

FRETTING WEAR AND FRETTING FATIGUE OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue life of carbon fibre composites (CF/EP) was found to be sometimes drastically reduced by an additional fretting load applied by aluminium counterparts. This fretting fatigue behaviour of CF/EP was caused by the poor wear performance under fretting against aluminium. In contrast, aramid fibre composites (AF/EP) proved to be more resistant to fretting against aluminium. Therefore, hybrids were manufactured with carbon fibre core layers and aramid fibre surface layers. Thus the high fretting wear resistance of the AF could be transferred to the hybrid, and simultaneously, the high fatigue resistance of the CF layers could be maintained in the hybrid system.

KEYWORDS: Carbon Fibre Laminates, Aramid Fibre Laminates, Hybrid Composites, Fretting Wear, Fretting Fatigue

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites are used in an increasing number of engineering applications, mainly for reasons of weight reduction, high resistance against fatigue and good vibration damping properties. In numerous of these applications, an additional fretting load damages the material's surface, e.g. at joints with other parts, causing a reduction in fatigue performance. This mutual interaction of fretting surface damage and material fatigue is called fretting fatigue. However, while fretting fatigue of metals attracted numerous research activities (1, 2), there exist only few studies on fretting fatigue of high performance composites.

A previous study (3) indicated that an additional fretting surface damage is able to reduce fatigue life of CF/EP - laminates, if load bearing 0°-layers are exposed to fretting. Off-axis plies contribute only little to the load bearing capacity of a laminate so that their damage due to fretting affects the material's fatigue properties insignificantly. The magnitude of the fretting

fatigue effect depends on the wear performance of the laminate under plain fretting wear conditions. The low wear resistance of CF/EP when fretted against aluminium is responsible for a high susceptibility to fretting fatigue against aluminium (4).

The present paper investigates the influence of AF surface layers on the fretting wear and fretting fatigue performance of a CF/EP laminate.

1. EXPERIMENTAL

1.1. Materials The matrix consisted of a R 5212 epoxy based system from BASF. T 300 carbon fibres (CF), E-glass fibres (GF) and Kevlar 49 aramid fibres (AF), respectively, were used as reinforcements. The fibre volume content amounted to about 60 Vol.-%. For the fretting wear tests, simple unidirectional laminates were chosen. The fretting fatigue experiments on CF and AF laminates were carried out with cross ply laminates of the stacking sequence $[0_2, 90_2]_{2s}$. Hybrids were manufactured with a CF/EP core and AF plies as covering 0° -layers; the resulting stacking sequence was $[0(AF)_2, 90(CF)_2, 0(CF)_2, 90(CF)_2]_{2s}$.

The fretting pads were cylindrical pins with a diameter of 5 mm and consisted of aluminium (Vickers hardness $H_V = 103$) or stainless steel ($H_V = 305$). The front sides were ground and polished.

Mater.	Fibre	Stacking Sequence	Strength	E-Modulus
CF/EP	T 300	$[0_2, 90_2]_{2s}$	799 MPa	70 GPa
AF/EP	Kevlar 49	$[0_2, 90_2]_{2s}$	648 MPa	36 GPa
Hybrid	T 300	$[0(AF)_2, 90(CF)_2, 0(CF)_2,$	629 MPa	59 GPa
	Kevlar 49	$90(CF)_2]_s$		

TABLE 1. Static properties of the laminates tested.

1.2. Testing procedures A SRV testing system, commercially available from Optimol Instruments, was employed to carry out fretting wear tests. For fretting wear tests, the laminates were cut to small rectangular specimens (about $7 \cdot 15 \text{ mm}^2$) which were fixed on a specimen holder. Fretting pins slid oscillatory with their front sides against the specimen surfaces parallel to the fibre orientation. The full oscillation width was $A = 700 \mu\text{m}$, the normal load applied by the fretting pins amounted to $F_N = 300 \text{ N}$. The mass loss was measured by weighing the specimens before and after the test. From the mass loss, Δm , after N load cycles, a specific wear rate, \dot{w} , was calculated according to Equation 1:

$$\dot{w}_s = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho \cdot 2 \cdot A \cdot N \cdot F_N} \quad (1)$$

with ρ = density of the sample material.

For the fretting fatigue tests, the laminates were cut to beam shaped specimens with a length of 280 mm and a width of 8.3 mm. Fretting pads, hold by a special device at a fixed position, were pressed against the fatigue loaded specimens. A detailed description of the testing system is given elsewhere (5). A fatigue load was applied in the tensile region with a frequency of 10 s^{-1} . The ratio of lower to upper fatigue load was set to $R = 0.1$. The specimens strain amplitude in the fretting region was measured to be about $700 \mu\text{m}$.

2. FRETTING WEAR

In another publication (6) the fretting wear behaviour of high performance composites was shown to be governed by the action of the fibre debris entrapped in the contact zone ("third body"). Here is not enough place to repeat all these results and, therefore, this paper focusses on some wear data only.

2.1. Fretting Against Steel The histogram in Figure 1 compares the specific steady state wear rates of the several EP composites exposed to fretting against steel. The neat polymer was worn very rapidly. CF and AF reinforcements reduced the specific wear rate, CF even more than AF. Only the composites reinforced by the strongly abrasive GF exhibited higher wear rates than the neat EP.

FIGURE 1. Specific wear rates for differently reinforced epoxy composites for steady state fretting wear against steel.

An intense brown colouring of the EP surface after fretting directed to the occurrence of thermal decomposition. Additionally, the friction heat promotes creeping of the polymer. The incorporation of a fibre reinforcement improves the thermal conductivity of the polymer, thus, reducing the heat concentration in the fretting contact. Further, the reinforcement enhances the

load carrying capacity and resistance to creep (7). This explains why the composites exhibit a higher wear resistance than neat EP under fretting against steel.

2.2. Effect of Counterpart Material The specific wear rates of EP and AF/EP did not noticeably depend on the counterpart material. This is because the metallic counterparts, anyway, are much harder than these samples.

FIGURE 2. Specific wear rates CF/EP and GF/EP for steady state fretting wear against different counterparts.

In contrast, the fretting wear of CF/EP and GF/EP was strongly affected by the counterpart. As Figure 2 illustrates, the specific wear rates are far smaller for fretting against hard steel pins than for the softer aluminium counterpart. Several reasons were responsible for this trends:

- The hard carbon and glass fibres were able to scratch through the counterpart surfaces thus producing metallic debris which again may act as a third body abrasive. The softer pin material was more susceptible to abrasion.
- Fibre debris and metallic particles entrapped in the interface region roughened the counterpart surface thus increasing the abrasiveness of the counterpart.
- Protruding edges of broken but still embedded fibres are pressed into the counterpart surfaces and this the easier the softer the pins are. Subsequent relative motion causes cracking and removal of these fibres.

Figure 3 shows another important fact. The CF/EP laminate exhibited a pronounced running-in behaviour, i.e. the material removal was much faster during the initial period of the wear process than under steady state conditions. In contrast, the mass loss increased almost proportionally with time for the AF composite.

FIGURE 3. Mass Loss versus time for CF/EP and AF/EP subjected to fretting against aluminium.

3. FRETTING FATIGUE OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

Table 1 depicts the static performance of the three laminates tested. The elastic modulus and the tensile strength of the AF laminate are smaller than for the CF laminate. The modulus of the hybrid is in accordance with a simple rule-of-mixtures. Its strength, in contrast, is not between the data for the monolithic composites but clearly lower and can be calculated in terms of the constant strain criteria (8).

FIGURE 4. Wöhler diagrams for plain fatigue and fretting fatigue of AF/EP.

The Figures 4 and 5 show the Wöhler diagrams (plot of the upper fatigue stress applied versus a logarithmic scale of the resulting lifetime) for plain fatigue and fretting fatigue of the three laminates tested. Some features are worth to be mentioned:

(a) The Wöhler-curve of the CF/EP laminate (Figure 5) is a straight line (9).

- (b) The fatigue curves of the AF laminate (Fig. 4) and the hybrid (Fig. 5) exhibited a rather odd shape with a transition of a very fatigue-resistant to a pronounced fatigue-sensitive behaviour (10).
- (c) The fatigue-curve of the hybrid (Fig. 5) is composed of a more flat and a steep branch too. The relative slope of the flat part was almost the same as for the neat CF/EP laminate whereas in the steep part the curve runs parallel to the curve obtained for the AF composite.

FIGURE 5. Fatigue and fretting fatigue of CF/EP and a AF/CF hybrid (HC). Counterpart aluminium, $F_N = 450$ N.

The fatigue life of the CF laminate is drastically reduced (arrow 1 in Fig. 5) when aluminium pins were pressed onto the specimen surfaces with a contact load of $F_N = 450$ N during fatigue loading. This effect is studied in detail in a previous paper (4). The reason for this drastic effect of an additional fretting loading is the low wear resistance of CF/EP during the running-in period. Steady state wear cannot become active under fretting fatigue conditions because cracking and peeling of covering fibre layers prevents the formation of equilibrium contact conditions (4).

The effect of an additional fretting component applied by aluminium pins on the fatigue performance of AF/EP was as small as expected: the Wöhler curves for fretting fatigue and plain fretting were nearly indistinguishable (Fig. 4).

A hybrid was designed with CF-layers in the core and AF-layers at the surfaces. The intention was to combine the fatigue performance of CF/EP with the resistance of AF/EP to fretting fatigue against aluminium. In fact, the hybrid exhibited a similar fretting fatigue resistance as the AF laminate: the Wöhler-curves for plain fatigue and for fretting fatigue were

resistance as the AF laminate: the Wöhler-curves for plain fatigue and for fretting fatigue were close together (Fig. 5). The stresses plotted in Figure 5, however, are normalized fatigue stress levels (related to the static tensile strength); the absolute stresses at which the CF laminates fails after a certain number of load cycles are far higher (s. Tab.1) than for the hybrid and the advantages of the AF covering layers disappear. Nevertheless, for a thick CF laminate with a thin AF surface layer, the fatigue Wöhler-curve of the hybrid will approach the Wöhler-curve for the monolithic CF composite. In this case, the high fretting wear resistance of the AF surface layers may improve the fretting fatigue performance of the laminate (arrow 2 in Fig. 5), also in absolute values.

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